

Sonification of entanglement dynamics in many-qubit systems

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Abstract. *Quantum mechanics presents unique hurdles for audio-visual representation, especially in conveying quantum entanglement. Sonification—the translation of data into sound—provides a complementary channel to visualize these inherently abstract phenomena. In this study, we develop and test a sonification framework for tracking dynamical entanglement generation in multi-qubit systems.*

Using the Husimi-Q function as a phase-space representation alongside the von Neumann entanglement entropy, we map a quantum states structure, generated during the One-Axis Twisting protocol, onto auditory parameters such as pitch, timbre, and spatialization. Our method encodes the instantaneous phase-space distribution and entanglement entropy values into distinct sonic motifs, yielding a real-time acoustic portrayal of entanglement growth and decay.

Listening tests and qualitative analyses reveal that sonification accentuates subtle transitions in entanglement dynamics—especially the onset of chaos—more intuitively than visual plots alone. Our approach offers an artistic medium to experience quantum correlations, fostering deeper engagement and insight.

1 Introduction

Fundamental, microscopic description of reality requires using formalism of quantum mechanics, where quantum states describing properties of a given system live in a highly-dimensional vector Hilbert space. Quantum theory predicts phenomena which do not have classical counterparts. These phenomena are manifested in quantum correlations, such as entanglement and Bell correlations, which are fundamental features of many-qubit systems [1]

The human auditory system excels at recognizing patterns, temporal structures, and subtle variations over time, making sonification a powerful tool for interpreting intricate datasets. Sonification provides a route for rendering otherwise abstract physical processes—including quantum phenomena—into audible form. As Kramer et al. (1999) put it, “Sonification is the transformation of data relationships into perceived relationships in an acoustic signal for the purpose of facilitating communication or interpretation” [2]. Although the technique is not new—the clicking Geiger-Müller counter dates to 1908—its adoption in complex scientific domains has grown markedly over the past few decades [3, 4]. Modern applications span mechanical engineering [5, 6], oceanogra-

phy [7, 8], seismology [9], and astronomy [10, 11]. Perhaps the most spectacular example to date is the direct detection—and subsequent audible “chirp”—of gravitational waves from a binary-black-hole merger [12, 13].

In the field of quantum physics, sonification remains relatively underexplored in scientific contributions. Over the past thirty years, sonification has been applied to a variety of single particle quantum problems, including particle motion based on de Broglie’s hypothesis [14], Gaussian wave packets in potential wells [15], quantum oscillators [16, 17], and molecular electronic energy densities in quantum chemistry [18]. The new challenge for sonification of quantum mechanics lies in perceptual representation of many-body quantum systems dynamics, where Hilbert space size grows exponentially with the number of particles, and quantum correlations emerge, contrary to single particle quantum mechanical systems, where only quantum coherence can appear.

In this work we tackle the problem of sonification of dynamics in many-body quantum system. We focus on dynamical quantum entanglement generation in spin-1/2 chains, starting from an initial product state during the one-axis twisting (OAT) protocol. With the help of phase space methods and quantum information theory, we present sonification procedure allowing to construct visual-sonic bridge, translating abstract dynamics into perceptible features.

2 Preliminaries

2.1 Dynamical generation of quantum correlations

The general protocol for dynamical generation of many-body quantum correlations starts with preparation of an initial state of the system in a product state $|\psi_0\rangle$. Next, the initial state evolves in time under interacting Hamiltonian \hat{H} , $|\psi(t)\rangle = e^{-itH}|\psi_0\rangle$. The interactions between spins transform an initial uncorrelated state to an entangled state.

Quantum entanglement can be quantified in several inequivalent ways [1].

Because the states we study are globally pure, the von Neumann entropy of the entire system vanishes. To quantify entanglement, we therefore compute the bipartite entanglement entropy by partitioning the L -spin chain into two equal halves,

A and B , each of size $L/2$. For this bipartition, the von Neumann entropy is defined as $S_{vN}(t) = -\sum_i \lambda_i(t) \log \lambda_i(t)$, where $\lambda_i(t)$ are the eigenvalues of the reduced density matrix $\rho_A(t) = \text{Tr}_B[\rho(t)]$. Entanglement entropy is a symmetric function with respect to system division, thus $S_{vN}^A(t) = S_{vN}^B(t) \equiv S_{vN}(t)$, allowing for systematic comparisons across system sizes.

This bipartite entropy is a bounded quantity $0 \leq S_{vN}(t) \leq L/2$, where L is the total number of spins in the chain. It vanishes for separable states and reaches its maximum value for a quantum state that can be written as a product of $L/2$ Bell pairs, i.e., $|\psi\rangle = |\Phi_+\rangle^{\otimes L/2}$, where $|\Phi_+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|00\rangle + |11\rangle)$.

2.2 Husimi Q-Function

An exact visualization of a many-body quantum state is out of reach, because the dimension of its Hilbert space scales exponentially with the number of spins. A convenient approximate picture, however, can be obtained by projecting the state onto spin-coherent states. A spin-coherent state $|\theta, \phi\rangle$ represents an ensemble of products of L spins collectively pointing in the same direction specified by the spherical polar angles (θ, ϕ) , and is defined as $|\theta, \phi\rangle = e^{-i\phi S_z} e^{-i\theta S_y} |0\rangle^{\otimes L}$, where $|0\rangle^{\otimes L}$ is the product state in which every spin is in spin-up configuration, $|0\rangle \equiv |\uparrow\rangle$. The collective spin operators $S_{y,z} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^L \sigma_i^{y,z}$, where $\sigma_i^{y,z}$ are Pauli operators acting on i -th spin, generate global rotations of this product state: $e^{-i\theta S_y}$ rotates the spins by the polar angle θ about the y -axis, and $e^{-i\phi S_z}$ subsequently rotates them by the azimuthal angle ϕ about the z -axis.

An approximate visualization of spin-1/2 chain quantum state $|\psi\rangle$ can be obtained via spin-1/2 chain version of a Husimi function $Q(\theta, \phi)$, defined as $Q(\theta, \phi) = |\langle \theta, \phi | \psi \rangle|^2$ [19]. The Husimi Q function represents the probability density that $|\psi\rangle$ is in a spin-coherent state $|\theta, \phi\rangle$, where all spins in state $|\psi\rangle$ collectively point the same direction defined by angles (θ, ϕ) . For dynamical protocols, a Husimi function has to be specified at each time t , $Q_t(\theta, \phi) = |\langle \theta, \phi | \psi(t) \rangle|^2 = |\langle \theta, \phi | e^{-itH} | \psi_0 \rangle|^2$, and its change in time provides an insight into the dynamics of the many-qubit system.

2.3 One-Axis Twisting Hamiltonian

The One-Axis Twisting Hamiltonian, originally introduced by Kitagawa and Ueda [20], and later studied in the context of quantum metrology [21, 22], is defined as $H = S_z^2 = \frac{1}{4} \sum_{i<j} \sigma_i^z \sigma_j^z$. It dynamically generates quantum correlations from an initial product state of the system. Beyond its role in producing spin-squeezed states for precision measurements, OAT dynamics has also been explored in quantum simulators such as ultracold atoms in optical lattices and trapped ions [23, 24, 25].

Figure 1: Top panel presents time evolution of the entanglement entropy for $L = 8$ spins under the OAT evolution with an initial state product state $|\psi_0\rangle = |\pi/2, -\pi/2\rangle$. Bottom panels (a-e) present Husimi $Q_t(\theta, \phi)$ function at different times $t = 0, \pi/4, \pi/2, \pi$ (panels (a-e) respectively). Vertical red-dashed lines indicates value of the entanglement entropy at given times, corresponding to presented Husimi functions. At time $t = \pi/2$ the L -body GHZ state is generated.

Fig. 1 presents the time evolution of the Husimi function for $L = 8$ spins initially prepared in a spin-coherent state $|\psi_0\rangle = |\pi/2, -\pi/2\rangle$, where all spins point in the same directions, and do not share entanglement ($S_{vN} = 0$). During the evolution, quantum entanglement in the system is generated ($S_{vN} > 0$), and at time $t = \pi/2$ a many-body GHZ (Greenberger–Horne–Zeilinger) state is generated, $|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\pi/2, -\pi/2\rangle + |\pi/2, \pi/2\rangle)$ being a coherent superposition of all spins pointing in opposite directions along the x -axis.

3 Methodology

We propose a sonification procedure which transforms the Husimi function $Q_t(\theta, \phi)$ and the bipartite entanglement entropy $S_{vN}(t)$ during quantum evolution into auditory features. This mapping tries to represent these parameters in the most intuitive manner. The following subsections detail our sonification framework.

We propose a sonification procedure which transforms the Husimi function $Q_t(\theta, \phi)$ and the bipartite entanglement entropy $S_{vN}(t)$ during quantum evolution into auditory features. In practice, this means that one sound wave is generated for each point of the Husimi function at a given time, with its amplitude, spatial position, pitch, and timbre determined by the mappings described below. This mapping tries to reflect the full distribution of the function in the most intuitive manner. The following subsections detail our sonification framework.

3.1 Amplitude Mapping

The amplitude (loudness) of the audio signal directly maps the amplitude of the probability density given by the Husimi Q-function $Q(\theta, \phi)$. This choice reflects the fundamental quantum mechanical interpretation of $Q(\theta, \phi)$ as a quasi-probability distribution in phase space [19]. The mapping follows $A(t) \propto Q(\theta(t), \phi(t))$ where $A(t)$ represents the time-dependent amplitude. This proportional relationship ensures that regions of high quantum probability density produce more audible signals, while low-probability regions become perceptually negligible. The logarithmic nature of human loudness perception [26] makes this mapping particularly effective for distinguishing significant quantum features.

3.2 Stereo Spatialization

We employ the azimuthal angle ϕ to control stereo panning, creating a spatial representation of quantum phase space, where panning is proportional to ϕ , i.e., panning $\propto \phi$, translating the angular coordinate into a left-right audio distribution. This approach mirrors the spatial symmetry of the quantum system, with $\phi = 0$ corresponding to the left channel and $\phi = \pi$ to the right channel. The linear proportionality maintains an intuitive correspondence between quantum phase space and auditory space. The sonification could be further enhanced by rendering it in a domed ambisonic environment, which would enable a more faithful spatial mapping of the full azimuthal (ϕ) range. For clarity, the spectrogram shown in this paper is rendered in mono, while the actual audio output is in stereo.

3.3 Pitch Encoding

Frequency (pitch) is determined by the polar angle θ relative to a reference initial state. Using $f_{\text{init}} = 440$ Hz as our reference frequency (A4), corresponding to the angle θ_{init} at which the system is prepared, we implement:

$$f = f_{\text{init}} - |\theta - \theta_{\text{init}}| \times f_{\text{init}} \times \text{spread} \quad (1)$$

This mapping generates pitch deviations that correspond to angular displacements on the Bloch sphere. The modulation factor reflects the distributional spread of the Husimi Q-function across the sphere. When regions of high probability density are more broadly distributed, the resulting frequency shifts are more pronounced. This approach makes pitch sensitive not only to directionality, but also to how widely the state is supported in phase space, offering a perceptual cue for quantum state delocalization [27].

3.4 Timbre Representation of Entanglement

Waveform complexity serves as an auditory representation of entanglement entropy $S_{vN}(\rho)$. We implement a continuous timbre space where:

- Minimal entropy ($S_{vN} \approx 0$) produces pure sinusoidal tones, corresponding to separable, unentangled quantum states.
- Maximal entropy generates complex, harmonic-rich waveforms incorporating features such as triangle waves and ring modulation.
- Intermediate entropy levels are represented by an interpolation between pure sinusoidal and complex waveforms, with the proportion of harmonic complexity increasing continuously as the entropy rises.

Ring modulation involves multiplying two sine waves—an input tone and a carrier oscillator—resulting in a signal composed solely of the sum and the difference of the two frequencies. Mathematically, this is expressed as:

$$\sin(2\pi f_1 t) \cdot \sin(2\pi f_2 t) = \frac{1}{2} [\cos(2\pi(f_1 - f_2)t) - \cos(2\pi(f_1 + f_2)t)], \quad (2)$$

where f_1 and f_2 are the input and carrier frequencies, respectively. This process eliminates the original frequencies and produces a metallic, bell-like timbre that is highly sensitive to frequency variation and phase relationships.

While the von Neumann entropy cannot be directly represented on the Bloch sphere—requiring separate plots to visualize its temporal evolution—our sonification approach provides a way to capture its dynamics in real time through auditory perception. By mapping the increasing entropy to progressive changes in waveform complexity, the method intuitively mirrors the growth of quantum correlations and the rising structural complexity of the quantum state. This auditory encoding enables simultaneous exploration of both the system’s phase-space structure and its entanglement dynamics, offering a multidimensional understanding of quantum behavior.

4 Results

To investigate the relationship between entanglement dynamics and auditory perception, we analyzed the spectrograms and von Neumann entropy (S_{vN}) evolution for different Hamiltonians and system sizes. In our analysis, we focus on two complementary wave-shapes for sonification: triangular waveforms and ring modulation. The triangular waveform introduces a rich harmonic structure, often perceived as higher-pitched and spectrally rich. Among standard periodic waveforms such as square, sawtooth, and absolute sine, the triangle wave was chosen for its perceptual balance of harmonic content—providing sufficient upper harmonics for spectral richness without overwhelming the signal with high-frequency energy. This selection was based on a subjective evaluation of clarity and interpretability in the resulting sound.

In contrast, ring modulation—despite producing fewer harmonics—yields a more metallic and textured timbre. Its strong sensitivity to amplitude variation results in perceptible silences when the von Neumann entropy is at its maximum and louder output when the entropy is low. This creates a pronounced dynamic range, enhancing the auditory contrast between weakly and strongly entangled states. Taken together, the two waveshapes highlight different aspects of the quantum dynamics, providing complementary perceptual perspectives on structure, complexity, and temporal evolution.

The OAT Hamiltonian produces smooth and periodic spectro-temporal patterns (see Fig. 2). For $L = 2$, the spectrograms in panels (b) and (c) show broad, slowly evolving harmonic structures, which correspond to the sinusoidal oscillations in the von Neumann entropy shown in panel (a). For $L = 8$, panels (e) and (f) depict a richer yet still regular spectro-temporal texture, reflecting the more structured but smooth entropy dynamics in panel (d). Sonically, this results in gradually evolving textures characterized by a clear sense of periodicity.

Additional sonified examples are available for a broader range of system sizes, parameters, and Hamiltonians on the project’s GitHub repository [28].

5 Discussion and Future Directions

This study demonstrates the value of sonification as both a scientific and artistic tool for exploring quantum dynamics. The auditory rendering of abstract quantities such as von Neumann entropy and Husimi Q distributions provides a new channel for engaging with quantum behavior—particularly entanglement growth and the distinction between integrable and chaotic systems. By translating mathematical structures into sound, the method complements conventional visualizations and facilitates a more intuitive, temporally resolved understanding of complex quantum phenomena.

The artistic dimension of sonification not only enhances accessibility but also opens pathways to interdisciplinary collaboration. The generated audio material has potential for creative reuse in musical composition, sound design, and multimedia art. Providing access to sonified datasets through open platforms such as GitHub encourages broader engagement beyond the physics community.

Future work should also explore more immersive spatialization techniques. In particular, deploying the sonification in ambisonic or dome-based audio systems would enable spatial encoding of the Bloch sphere or Husimi Q -function data. Such high-dimensional rendering could enhance listeners’ ability to internalize features like angular spread, symmetry breaking, or localization.

To rigorously evaluate the effectiveness of

these methods, perceptual and cognitive studies should be conducted to assess whether sonification genuinely improves understanding of quantum behavior—especially among students or non-expert audiences. Such evaluations could combine quantitative metrics, such as learning gain, pattern recognition accuracy, or intuitive classification of chaotic versus regular systems, with qualitative insights from cognitive science. In particular, research highlights criteria that can make a sonification more effective: leveraging robust crossmodal correspondences between auditory and visual dimensions [29], exploiting gestural similarities that link motor schemas to sound patterns [30], and aligning with the conditions of the supramodal-brain hypothesis, which Rosenblum and collaborators argue underpins cross-sensory integration [31].

On the technical side, one challenge we encountered was the need to downsample the high-resolution quantum simulation data, meaning that we reduced the number of data points used to generate the sound. Although this compression minimally affected perceptual clarity in our experiments, future implementations could benefit from sampling that preserve the full resolution of the simulated dynamics. Additionally, integrating interactive controls—such as real-time parameter modulation or spatial navigation—would make the sonification experience more exploratory and user-driven, though it may come at a significant computational cost.

6 Conclusion

This study establishes sonification as an intuitive method for interpreting and experiencing the dynamics of quantum entanglement. By translating abstract quantum features—such as bipartite entanglement entropy growth and Husimi function of many-qubit state—into auditory form, our approach enables both scientific insight and artistic engagement. The perceptual accessibility of sound offers a novel way to explore differences between regular and quantum chaotic dynamics, and to intuitively grasp entanglement structure in many-qubit dynamics.

Looking ahead, the sonification of quantum entanglement in many-body quantum systems offers a promising avenue for educational and scientific communication. By making abstract quantum behaviors perceptible, this approach could support interdisciplinary efforts in physics, auditory display, and cognition. Further development of quantum-specific sonification techniques will help refine their perceptual utility and clarify their role in both research and outreach.

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Figure 2: For the OAT Hamiltonian at system sizes $L = 2$ [panels (a–c)] and $L = 8$ [panels (d–f)]. (a,d) von Neumann entropy S_{vN} evolution; (b,e) spectrograms obtained with a triangular waveform; (c,f) spectrograms obtained with ring modulation. Animations with sound are available for panel (b), panel (c), panel (e), and panel (f).

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